

CODECHECK: An Open Science initiative for the independent execution of computations underlying research articles during peer review to improve reproducibility

Daniel Nüst ^{2,*}

¹Institute for Geoinformatics, University of Münster, Germany; daniel.nuest@uni-muenster.de

²Department of Applied Mathematics and Theoretical Physics, University of Cambridge, UK; sje30@cam.ac.uk

*Corresponding authors

Public project for this article is at <https://github.com/codecheckers/paper>.

Abstract The traditional scientific paper falls short of effectively communicating computational research. To help improve this situation, we propose a system by which the computational workflows underlying research articles are checked. The CODECHECK system uses open infrastructure and tools and can be integrated into review and publication processes in multiple ways. We describe these integrations along multiple dimensions (importance, who, openness, when). In collaboration with academic publishers and conferences, we demonstrate CODECHECK with 25 reproductions of diverse scientific publications. These CODECHECKs show that asking for reproducible workflows during a collaborative review can effectively improve executability. While CODECHECK has clear limitations, it may represent a building block in Open Science and publishing ecosystems for improving the reproducibility, appreciation, and, potentially, the quality of non-textual research artefacts.

Keywords

reproducible research, Open Science, peer review, reproducibility, code sharing, data sharing, quality control, scholarly publishing

Abbreviations

ACM: Association for Computing Machinery; ECRs: Early Career Researchers; RCR: Replicated Computational Results; TOMS: Transactions on Mathematical Software.

Introduction

Many areas of scientific research use computations to simulate or analyse their data. These complex computations are difficult to explain coherently in a paper [1]. To complement the traditional route of sharing research by writing papers, there is a growing demand to share the underlying artefacts, notably code and datasets, so that others can inspect, reproduce or expand that work (see Figure 1). Early proponents of this initiative were Buckheit and Donoho [2, 3], who noted: “*An article about computational science in a scientific publication is not the scholarship itself, it is merely **advertising** of the scholarship. The actual scholarship is the complete software development environment and the complete set of instructions which generated the figures.*”

If researchers start sharing more artefacts, how might these artefacts be examined to ensure that they do what they claim? For example, although scientific journals now require a data sharing statement that outlines what data the authors have (or will) share, journals implement this differently. On one hand, journals have been created to accept “data papers” (e.g., *Scientific Data*, *Earth System Science Data*, *Geoscience Data Journal*, *Biodiversity Data Journal*, *Journal of Open Psychology Data*, *Open Data Journal for Agricultural Research*, *Journal of Open Health Data*); these journals have established rigorous procedures by which data are validated according to standards in each field. On the other hand, many journals still allow authors to state “Data available upon reasonable request”. Authors, while possibly well intentioned at the time of writing the article, often cannot provide data when requested as data disappears over time [4].

Given that data are not routinely shared, what hope might there be for sharing computer programs? Both data and software are required to validate a computational analysis; data can be seen as inert whereas code requires an environment to be run in. This makes software harder to share. Our experience is that researchers offer several reasons for why code is not shared, e.g., “there is no documentation”, “I cannot maintain it”, or “I do not want to give away my code to competitors”. Our view is that sharing code, wherever possible, is good for the community and the individual [5, 6]. Having code and data openly available, and archived, provides a valuable resource for others to learn from, even if the code is broken or lacks documentation. However, with a little effort, we believe that if an independent person can re-run the programs, this is worth documenting and that this reduces the barrier to evaluating non-text research materials. Just as data journals’ validations of data and all journals’ peer review provides a “baseline reassurance”, i.e., that a paper has been checked by someone with an understanding of the topic [7], the same baseline could be provided for the workflow underlying a paper. With this in mind, we have developed a set of principles and an example workflow that provides a pragmatic way of checking that a paper’s code works, i.e., it is reproducible following the Claerbout/Donoho/Peng terminology [8].

Here we offer a thorough description of a process and its variations to integrate a much-needed evaluation of computational reproducibility into peer review, and we demonstrate its feasibility by means of 25 reproductions across scientific disciplines. We call this system CODECHECK.

Images: Noto Emoji (Apache 2.0)

Figure 1. The inverse problem in reproducible research. The left half of the diagram shows a diverse range of materials used within a laboratory. These materials are often then condensed for sharing with the outside world via the research paper, a static PDF document. Working backwards from the PDF to the underlying materials is impossible. This prohibits reuse and is not only non-transparent for a specific paper but is also ineffective for science as a whole. By sharing the materials on the left, others outside the lab can enhance this work.

What is a CODECHECK?

Workflow and people

CODECHECK is best demonstrated by way of our example workflow, and later we expand on the underlying principles. The workflow involves three groups of people: (1) the **author** of a paper providing the code to be checked, (2) the **publisher** of a journal interested in publishing the author's paper, and (3) the **codechecker**, who checks that the author's code works. The six-step workflow we have refined is shown in Figure 2. In this article, we also refer to a **peer-reviewer** who is independent of this process, and performs the traditional academic review of the content of an article.

Step 1: The author submits their manuscript along with the code and data to the publisher. The code and data need not be openly available at this point. However, in many cases the code and data may be published on a code hosting platform, such as GitHub or GitLab. Ideally, the author is expecting the CODECHECK and prepares for it, e.g., by asking a colleague to attempt a reproduction, and providing a set of instructions on how to re-run the workflow.

Step 2: The publisher finds a codechecker to check the code. This is analogous to the publisher finding one or more peer-reviewers to evaluate the paper, except we suggest that the codechecker and the author talk directly to each other.

Step 3: The codechecker runs the code, based on instructions provided by the author. They check if some or all of the results from the paper can be reproduced. If there are any problems running the code, the codechecker asks the author for help, updates, or further documentation. The burden to provide reproducible material lies with the author. The codechecker then tries to run the code again. This process iterates until either the codechecker is successful, or the codechecker concludes

Figure 3. The dimensions of implementing a CODECHECK process.

Step 5: The certificate and auxiliary files created during the check, e.g., a specification of a computing environment, data subsets or helper scripts, and the original code and data get deposited in an open archive unless restrictions (data size, license or sensitivity) apply. Currently, codecheckers deposit the material on Zenodo themselves, but a publisher may complete this step after integrating CODECHECK into its review process. A badge or other visual aid may be added to the deposit and the paper and link to the certificate. Although a badge simplifies the CODECHECK into a binary value and risks introducing confusion regarding the extent of the check, a badge provides recognition value and acknowledges the completed CODECHECK. The badge and the actual check are incentives for undertaking the effort needed to provide a reproducible workflow.

Step 6: The publisher can, depending on the timing, provide the certificate to peer-reviewers or editors or publish it and link between certificate, paper, and any repositories. Currently, the codechecker creates these connections on Zenodo. They appear as links with a relationship type on the Zenodo landing page for a certificate, e.g., the “related identifiers” and “alternate identifiers” of certificate 2020-025 [14]. The publisher also credits the codechecker’s work by depositing the activity in scholarly profiles, such as ORCID (see peer review contributions in ORCID records, <https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/articles/360006971333-Peer-Review>). The publisher also ensures proper publication metadata, e.g., links from the certificate repository to the published paper or the original code repository.

Variations

Dimensions of CODECHECK workflows

Our workflow is just one of many possibilities of a CODECHECK workflow. Here we consider several dimensions in a space of possible CODECHECK workflows (Figure 3). These aspects touch on timing, responsibilities, and transparency.

When to do a CODECHECK and with what importance?

The time at which a CODECHECK is done and its ascribed importance are closely connected, so we describe the dimensions *When* and *Importance* together. The earlier a CODECHECK happens in the publishing process, the more it can affect editorial decisions: Is a paper published, sent back for revisions, or rejected? Even earlier checks, i.e., a CODECHECK of a preprint, may help to improve the workflow itself, even before a publisher is involved. As such, codechecking papers could be part of a preprint server's policy or initiated by interested authors.

Publishers could introduce a CODECHECK as a **strict prerequisite**. As this can reduce the workload of reviewers, such a check should occur early in the review process. Yet, the later in the review process the check happens, the easier is it to allow bidirectional communication between the author and codechecker, e.g., because the author might already be notified of the paper's acceptance and may be more willing to share materials online closer to the paper's publication date. A **pre-review** CODECHECK means editors would send a submission for peer review only if it passes the check, or include the certificate in the submission package provided to peer-reviewers. Peer-reviewers may then judge the relevance of the computations for the results of the work.

A CODECHECK may also be conducted in **parallel** to the academic peer review. This puts less burden on the turnaround time for the CODECHECK, yet it only makes the outcomes available during the final consideration by the handling editor. The check could also be assigned after suggestion by a reviewer, which would remove the need for submissions to undergo a pre-review screening. However, soliciting such a "specialist review" is much less desirable than having a regular CODECHECK, thus avoiding the situation in which some submissions get special treatment. In both cases, the editor's decision could be based both on CODECHECK and peer-review reports.

A **post-acceptance** CODECHECK would have the smallest impact on editorial decisions and may simply provide **extra merit** on top of the submission's acceptance. This is the least impactful solution in which all material is still evaluated and the results of the check are properly acknowledged, because the check can be completed before publication of the paper. The GIScience checks (see below) falls into this category: By displaying a badge on the volume and article landing pages, the AGILE conference highlights articles whose reproducibility was confirmed. Similarly, in collaborations with journals, some GIScience articles were checked whilst authors worked on revisions.

A CODECHECK may also be conducted **post-publication**, though this requires an update to the article and article metadata to reference the check so that readers can find the CODECHECK. In general, publishers hesitate to make such revisions to published articles. We do not prefer this option as it has the least impact on current publishing practices and downplays the importance of reproducible workflows for ensuring good scientific practice.

Enhancing existing processes with CODECHECKS allows communities to gradually transition towards more open practices. When integrating a CODECHECK into existing review and publication processes, the *turnaround time* is crucial. Depending on when and who conducts the check, it might

be done quickly or it might delay publication. We found that a CODECHECK generally takes 2–5 hours, with some outliers on the higher end. This time includes writing and publishing the certificate but excludes actual computation time, some of which took days. These efforts are comparable to the time needed to peer review a submission, which aligns with the efforts some volunteer codecheckers are willing to make. Currently, there is considerable amount of communicating about the process, especially regarding who publishes which document when, so that proper cross-referencing between paper and certificate is ensured via persistent identifiers. When integrated into a peer review platform, this handling of documents should become much more streamlined.

Openness, or “Who knows who?”

Anonymity is broadly discussed, especially in the push towards open peer review as part of the Open Science movement (cf. [15]). Without taking a strong stance on this topic, our motivation behind CODECHECK for higher transparency and reproducibility does indeed favour a more open review process. However, anonymity can protect individuals [16], e.g., junior scientists. The negative effects of a signed review may be reduced if a CODECHECK is not relevant for a journal’s decision to accept or reject, but that is, of course, not desirable when the goal is higher transparency and reproducibility. Instead, CODECHECK is a technical process that should generally find fixable problems; it is not aimed at giving an opinion or identifying a faulty approach. If passing a CODECHECK becomes mandatory, full transparency may need revisiting as the relations between authors and codecheckers would fall under the same social and community challenges as open peer review (cf. [17]).

The technical nature of the check and the challenge of providing sufficient documentation is why we see great benefits in bidirectional communication between author and codechecker. Instead of trying to fix problems or guess the next step, the codechecker can ask the author to rework the documentation or update code. Instead of struggling to provide perfect instructions and as a result possibly not sharing any code or data, the author can make a best effort to document sufficiently. Authors and readers can profit from a codecheckers’ experience and approach, as during the check they may create useful and instructive files, e.g., a machine-readable computing environment specification. While communication between author and codechecker may be anonymised via the publisher, it most likely only helps to protect the identity of the codechecker, because code is hard to anonymise. Therefore, the most effective and desirable situation for the stakeholders is to hold a open and collaborative CODECHECK. The contributions by the codechecker may even be integrated into the code of the workflow and be acknowledged as code commits. This way, proper credit can be given within the research software development community.

Who does the CODECHECK?

Just as with peer-reviewers, a potential codechecker should have the right skills and availability to do the work. Ideally, the codechecker has a matching code *and* domain expertise to the paper, although

a well-documented workflow should be executable by any computationally-competent person. Naturally, the more prerequisite knowledge the codechecker has, the quicker they can understand the goals and mechanics of an analysis. From our experiences, the priority should be given to matching technical expertise first, as lacking knowledge in setting up a computing environment with a particular language or tool is much more of a problem than assessing the outcome, e.g., comparing created figures with the original, without an in-depth understanding of the domain. The depth of the check will mostly be driven by the time required and expertise of the checker, though in general, we expect a CODECHECK to consider reproducibility of the results above performance of the code.

Codecheckers could be drawn from a regular pool of **peer-reviewers**, or from a special group of **reproducibility reviewers** via specific roles such as **reproducibility editors**, or **editorial staff** with a publisher. One codechecker is sufficient to verify the workflow since it is mostly a factual process. Code usually harbours systematic and repeatable mistakes and is thereby more reliable and auditable than processes controlled by humans [18], e.g., in a laboratory. If however publication of the paper depends on the CODECHECK, a second opinion may be required.

We also see a great opportunity to involve *early-career researchers* (ECRs) as codecheckers. ECRs arguably have a high interest in learning about new tools and technologies, to build up their own expertise. CODECHECK offers a way for ECRs to gain insights into new research and highlight the importance of reproduction. *ReScience X*, a journal devoted to reproduction and replication experiments [19], shares an interest in this combination. ECRs are also often familiar with new technologies, thus also making them likely to author CODECHECK-ready manuscripts. A supporting data point for ECRs as early adopters is that they are responsible for 77% of 141 registered reports that were submitted [20]. As ECRs are introduced to peer review as codecheckers, they may transition into the role of peer-reviewer over time. Overall, we see several opportunities and benefits to setting up a new process for codechecking with a clear commitment to openness and transparency, independent of the current peer review process (see *Openness* dimension).

The codechecker could be a member of **editorial staff**; this is the most controlled but also resource-intensive option. Such a resource commitment would show that publishers are investing in reproducibility, yet this commitment may be hard for small publishers. These codecheckers could be fully integrated into internal workflows. Credit for doing the codecheck is also achieved, as it is part of their duties. By contrast, it is useful for researchers to be publicly credited for their reviewing activity. A regular review may be listed in public databases (e.g., ORCID, see Step 6 above, or commercial offerings such as Publons, <https://publons.com/>, and ReviewerCredits, <https://www.reviewercredits.com/>); a codechecker could be similarly listed.

The codechecker community has over 20 volunteers who signed up in the last year, see <https://github.com/codecheckers/codecheckers/>. Their motivations, mentioned in the registration information at <https://github.com/codecheckers/codecheckers/labels/registration>, include: supporting reproducible research and Open Science, improve coding skills, gaining experience in

helping scientists with their code, encouraging a sharing culture, and learning from other people's mistakes; many are also motivated simply by curiosity. We see benefits to an open shared list of codecheckers across journals rather than a private in-house group, as this may allow for better matches regarding expertise and workload sharing. This community can establish CODECHECK as a viable option for independent no-cost Open Access journals.

Core principles

The workflow and variations outlined describe our current views on how code could be checked. They are not immutable, but we believe the following core principles underpin our CODECHECK process:

1. Codecheckers record but don't investigate or fix.

The codechecker follows the author's instructions to run the code. If instructions are unclear, or if code does not run, the codechecker tells the author. We believe that the job of the codechecker is not to fix these problems but simply to report them to the author and await a fix. The level of documentation required for third parties to reproduce a workflow is hard to get right, and too often this uncertainty leads researchers to give up and not document it at all. The conversation with a codechecker fixes this problem.

2. Communication between humans is key.

Some code may work without any interaction, e.g. [21], but often there are hidden dependencies that need adjusting for a particular system. Allowing the codechecker to communicate directly and openly with the author make this process as constructive as possible; routing this conversation (possibly anonymously) through a publisher would introduce delays and inhibit community building.

3. Credit is given to codecheckers.

The value of performing a CODECHECK is comparable to that of a peer review, and it may require a similar amount of time. Therefore, the codechecker's activity should be recorded, ideally in the published paper. The public record can be realised by publishing the certificate in a citable form (i.e., with a DOI), by listing codecheckers on the journal's website or, ideally, by publishing the checks alongside peer review activities in public databases.

4. Workflows must be auditable.

The codechecker should have sufficient material to validate the workflow outputs submitted by the authors. Stark [22] calls this "preproducibility" and the ICERM report [11] defines the level "Auditable Research" similarly. Communities can establish their own good practices or adapt generic concepts and practical tools, such as publishing all building blocks of science in a research compendium (cf. <https://research-compendium.science/>) or "repro-pack" [23]. A completed check means that code could be executed at least once using the provided instructions, and, therefore, all code and data was given and could be investigated more deeply or extended in the future. Ideally, this is a "one click" step, but achieving this requires particular skills and a sufficient level of documentation for third parties. Furthermore, automation may lead to people gaming the system or reliance on

technology, which can often hide important details. All such aspects can reduce the understandability of the material, so we estimate our approach to codechecking, done without automation and with open human communication, to be a simple way to ensure long-term transparency and usefulness. We acknowledge that others have argued in favour of bitwise reproducibility because, in the long run, it can be automated (e.g., <https://twitter.com/khinsen/status/1242842759733665799>), but until then we need CODECHECK's approach.

5. Open by default and transitional by disposition.

Unless there are strong reasons to the contrary (e.g., sensitive data on human subjects), all code and data, both from author and codechecker, will be made freely available when the certificate is published. Openness is not required for the paper itself, to accommodate journals in their transition to Open Access models. The code and data publication should follow community good practices. Ultimately we may find that CODECHECK activities are subsumed within peer review.

Implementation

Register

To date we have created 25 certificates (Table 1) falling into three broad themes: (1) classic and current papers from computational neuroscience, (2) COVID-19 modelling preprints, and (3) GIScience. The first theme was an initial set of papers used to explore the concept of CODECHECK. The idea was to take well-known articles from a domain of interest (Neuroscience). Our first CODECHECK (certificate number 2020-001) was performed before publication on an article for the journal *GigaScience*, which visualized the outputs from a family of supervised classification algorithms.

The second theme was a response to the COVID-19 pandemic, selecting papers that predicted outcomes. The checks were solicited through community interaction or by our initiative rather than requested from journals. Some certificates were since acknowledged in the accepted papers [24, 25]. In particular, we codechecked the well-known Imperial college model of UK lockdown procedures from March 2020, demonstrating that the model results were reproducible [26, 27].

The third theme represents co-author DN's service as a Reproducibility Reviewer at the AGILE conference series, where the *Reproducible AGILE* Initiative [28] independently established a process for reproducing workflows at the AGILE conference series [29]. While using slightly different terms and infrastructure ("reproducibility reports" are published on the Open Science Framework instead of certificates on Zenodo) AGILE reproducibility reviews adhere to CODECHECK principles. A few checks were also completed as part of peer reviews for GIScience journals.

Annotated certificate and check metadata

After running the workflow, the codechecker writes a certificate stating which outputs from the original article, i.e., numbers, figures or tables, could be reproduced. This certificate is made openly

Certificate	Research area	Description
2020-001 [30]	Machine learning	Code for benchmarking ML classification tool checked post acceptance of manuscript and before its publication in <i>Gigascience</i> [31].
2020-002 [32]	Neuroscience	Code written for this project checked by second project member as demonstration using paper from 1997 showing unsupervised learning from natural images [33].
2020-003 [34]	Neuroscience	Code written for this project checked by second project member as demonstration using classic paper on models of associative memory [35].
2020-004 [36]	Neuroscience	Code written for this project checked by second project member as demonstration using classic paper on cart-pole balancing problem [37].
2020-005 [38]	Neuroscience	Check of independent reimplementations of spike-timing-dependent plasticity (STDP) model [39] conducted as demonstration for this paper.
2020-006 [40]	Neuroscience	Check of independent reimplementations of a generalized linear integrate-and-fire neural model [41] conducted as demonstration for this paper.
2020-007 [42]	Neuroscience	Check of independent reimplementations of analysing spike patterns of neurons [43] conducted as demonstration for this paper.
2020-008 [44]	COVID-19	Code for modelling of interventions on COVID-19 cases in the UK checked at preprint stage [45] and later published [24].
2020-009 [46]	COVID-19	Code for analysis of effectiveness of measures to reduce transmission of SARS-CoV-2 checked as preprint [47] and later published [25].
2020-010 [27]	COVID-19	Code for analysis of non-pharmaceutical interventions (Report 9) checked as a preprint [48].
2020-011 [49]	COVID-19	Code for modelling of COVID-19 spread across Europe was provided by authors and checked while paper was in press [50].
2020-012 [51]	COVID-19	Code for modelling of COVID-19 spread across the USA was checked as preprint [52] and later published [53].
2020-013 [21]	Neuroscience	Code for analysis of rest-activity patterns in people without con-mediated vision was checked as a preprint [54] after direct contact with the authors.
2020-014 [55]	Neuroscience	Code for analysis of perturbation patterns of neural activity was checked after publication as part of publisher collaboration [56].
2020-015 [57]	Neuroscience	Code for a neural network model for human focal seizures was checked after publication as part of publisher collaboration [58].
2020-016 [59]	GIScience	Code for models demonstrating the Modifiable Area Unit Problem (MAUP) in spatial data science [60] was checked during peer review.
2020-017 [61]	GIScience	Code for spatial data handling, analysis, and visualisation using a variety of R packages [62] was checked after peer review before publication.
2020-018 [63]	GIScience	AGILE conference reproducibility report using a demonstration data subset with cellular automaton for modeling dynamic phenomena [64].
2020-019 [65]	GIScience	AGILE conference reproducibility report with subsampled dataset for reachability analysis of suburban transportation using shared cars [66].
2020-020 [67]	GIScience	AGILE conference reproducibility report using a container for checking in-database windows operators for processing spatio-temporal data [68].
2020-021 [69]	GIScience	AGILE conference reproducibility report checking code for comparing supervised machine learning models for spatial nominal entity recognition [70].
2020-022 [71]	GIScience	AGILE conference reproducibility report checking code for visualising text analysis on intents and concepts from geo-analytic questions [72].
2020-023 [73]	GIScience	AGILE conference reproducibility report on analysis of spatial footprints of geo-tagged extreme weather events from social media [74].
2020-024 [75]	Neuroscience	Code for multi-agent system for concept drift detection in electromyography [76] was checked during peer review.
2020-025 [14]	GIScience	Adaptation and application of Local Indicators for Categorical Data (LICD) to archaeological data [77] was checked after peer review before publication.

Table 1. Register of completed certificates as of December 2020. An interactive version is available at <http://codecheck.org.uk/register>.

available so that everyone can see which elements were reproduced and what limitations or issues were found. The certificate links to code and data used by the codechecker, allowing others to build on the work. The format of the certificates evolved during the project, as we learnt to automate different aspects of the certification. The metadata is stored in a machine-readable structured file in YAML, the CODECHECK configuration file `codecheck.yml`. The technical specification of the CODECHECK configuration file is published at <https://codecheck.org.uk/spec/config/latest/>. The configuration file enables current and future automation of workflows and meta-analyses.

Figure 4 shows pages 1–4 (of 10) of an example certificate to check predictions of COVID-19 spread across the USA [51, 52]. Figure 4A shows the certificate number and its DOI, which points to the certificate and any supplemental files on Zenodo. The CODECHECK logo is added for recognition and to denote successful reproduction. Figure 4B provides the key metadata extracted from `codecheck.yml`; it names the paper that was checked (title, DOI), the authors, the codechecker, when the check was performed, and where code/data are available. Figure 4C shows a textual summary of how the CODECHECK was performed and key findings. Figure 4D (page 2 of the certificate) shows the outputs that were generated based on the MANIFEST of output files in the CODECHECK. It shows the file name (Output), the description stating to which figure/table each file should be compared in the original paper (Comment), and the file size. Page 3 of the certificate, (Figure 4E) gives detailed notes from the codechecker, here documenting what steps were needed to run the code and that the code took about 17 hours to complete. Finally, page 4 of the certificate shows the first output generated by the CODECHECK (Figure 4F). In this case, the figure matched figure 4 of [52]. The remaining pages of the certificate show other outputs and the computing environment in which the certificate itself was created (not shown here).

Tools and resources

We use freely available infrastructure, GitHub and Zenodo, to run our system. The **codecheckers** GitHub organisation at <https://github.com/codecheckers> contains projects for managing the project website, the codecheckers community and its discussions, code repositories, and the main register of CODECHECKs. Both the project website <https://codecheck.org.uk/> and the register at <https://codecheck.org.uk/register> are hosted as GitHub pages. The register database is a single table in CSV format that connects the certificate identifier with the repository associated with a CODECHECK. Each of these repositories, which currently can be hosted on GitHub or Open Science Framework, contains the CODECHECK metadata file `codecheck.yml`. The register further contains a column for the type of check, e.g., community, journal, or conference, and the respective GitHub issue where communications and assignments around a specific check are organised. No information is duplicated between the register and the metadata files. The continuous integration infrastructure of GitHub, GitHub Actions, is used to automate generation of the register. **Zenodo** is our preferred open repository for storing certificates. It mints DOIs for deposits and ensures long-

A CODECHECK certificate 2020-012
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3893617>

B

Item	Value
Title	Report 23: State-level tracking of COVID-19 in the United States version 2 (28-05-2020)
Authors	H Juliette T Linwin, Swapnil Mishra, Valerie C Bradley, et al.
Reference	https://dx.doi.org/10.25561/79231
Codechecker	Stephen J. Eglen
Date of check	2020-06-14 14:00:00
Summary	R code for this paper shared with an earlier codecheck certificate (2020-011) from the same codebase.
Repository	https://github.com/sjc30/covid19model-report23

Table 1: CODECHECK summary

C Summary

The key findings in the “Report 23” from Imperial College were reproducible. I was able to re-run their code and generate qualitatively similar results to those shown in their manuscript. Differences in absolute values in results are due to the stochastic nature of the analysis. All code to reproduce the data worked as expected, and all key datasets were provided. I was able to regenerate the results in Figures 4–8 of the manuscript; code for Figures 1–3 was not available. (I did not attempt to go through all of the figures in the appendix, although Appendix D is an expanded version of Figure 6, showing summaries of each state.) The only significant complication in this reproduction was that some of the figures required the installation of system libraries. The final computations took about 17 hours on a multicore workstation.

In some cases, figures directly matched the layout in the manuscript; however, sometimes the figures have been post-processed as there are differences in layout. For example, in Figure 4 of the manuscript, the states have been re-ordered vertically in order of the value of R_t . Likewise, in Figure 8, the plots have been expanded out over three columns.

D

Output	Comment	Size (b)
usa/figures/rt_point__1006697_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 4	10841
usa/figures/1006697_rt_map_chloropleth_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 5	77748
usa/figures/WA_three_panel_1006697_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 6 (Washington)	15409
usa/figures/NY_three_panel_1006697_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 6 (New York)	14703
usa/figures/MA_three_panel_1006697_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 6 (Massachusetts)	14472
usa/figures/FL_three_panel_1006697_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 6 (Florida)	14642
usa/figures/CA_three_panel_1006697_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 6 (California)	14798
usa/figures/1006697_infectiousness_regions_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 7	38005
usa/figures/WA_scenarios_56_0_20_40_1006697_deaths_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 8 (Washington)	10032
usa/figures/NY_scenarios_56_0_20_40_1006697_deaths_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 8 (New York)	10582
usa/figures/MA_scenarios_56_0_20_40_1006697_deaths_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 8 (Massachusetts)	10432
usa/figures/FL_scenarios_56_0_20_40_1006697_deaths_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 8 (Florida)	10039
usa/figures/CA_scenarios_56_0_20_40_1006697_deaths_.pdf	Manuscript Figure 8 (California)	10052

Table 2: Summary of output files generated

E CODECHECKER notes

The github repository <https://github.com/ImperialCollegeLondon/covid19model> was cloned, and renamed to “sjc30/covid19model-report23”. (I could not clone the project into the Github codecheckers group, as you cannot have two forks of the same project in the same organisation.)

This reproduction was performed after finishing the related certificate 2020-011; details of setting up the R environment are described in that certificate.

However, the R environment described was insufficient, as it didn't include *geofacet* and *rgdal* packages which needed system libraries to install. Once the sysadmin had installed extra libraries for *unitedevs2* and *gdal*, I needed to run the following adhoc module provided locally:

```
module load ./gdal-2.1.2
install.packages("rgdal")
install.packages("geofacet")
install.packages("denstrip") #for plotting
```

An initial run of the FULL model didn't work because I had an older version of *rstan* package; this was upgraded to 2.19.3. The simulations were tested by running the simulation directly on a workstation:

```
time Rscript base-usa.r
```

Running the test mode took 41 minutes and generated outputs.

```
time Rscript base-usa.r -F
```

The final run time was 1020 minutes (17 hours). The code for reproducing figures 1,2 and 3 was not available in the repository, but all other key figures could be regenerated.

F

Figure C1: Manuscript Figure 4

Figure 4. Annotated certificate 2020-012 [51] (first four pages only).

term availability of all digital artefacts related to the project. The CODECHECK community on Zenodo is available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/codecheck/>. It holds certificates, the regularly archived register [78], and other material related to CODECHECK.

A **custom R package**, `codecheck`, automates repetitive tasks around authoring certificates and managing the register. The package is published at <https://github.com/codecheckers/codecheck> under MIT license [79]. It includes scripts to deposit certificates and related files to Zenodo using the R package `zen4R` [80] and for the register update process outlined above. Codecheckers can ignore this package, and use their own tools for creating and depositing the certificate. This flexibility accommodates different skill sets and unforeseen technical advances or challenges.

These tools and resources demonstrate that a CODECHECK process can be managed on freely available platforms. Automation of some aspects may improve turnaround time. Our main resource requirements are the **humans** needed for managing the project and processes and the codecheckers. All contributions currently rely on (partly grant-based) public funding and volunteering.

Related work

The journal *ACM Transactions on Mathematical Software (TOMS)* recently established a “Replicated Computational Results” (RCR) review process [81], where “replicable” is the same as our use of “reproducible”. Fifteen RCR Reports have been published so far (search on <https://search.crossref.org/> with the term "Replicated Computations Results (RCR) Report" on 2020-12-10). and the process is being extended extended to the ACM journal *Transactions on Modeling and Computer Simulation*. The TOMS RCR follows CODECHECK principles 1-4, although our work was independently developed of theirs. The TOMS editorial [81] shares similar concerns about selection of reviewers, as we discussed above. Unlike existing CODECHECK certificates, the RCR reports undergo editorial review. Publication of the RCR report recognises the efforts of the reproducing person, while the potential for this motive to be a conflict of interest is acknowledged. TOMS also recognises reviewer activity in a partnership with Publons (see <https://authors.acm.org/author-services/publons>). This activity in the ACM journals can be seen as one possible workflow within a CODECHECK system, and clearly shares much in spirit. CODECHECK, however, specifically aims to give codecheckers recognition as reviewers. In our view, the reviewer role removes the possible conflict of interest while keeping the public acknowledgement. Specific to the field of mathematics, the RCR is also expected to apply a review of the software itself if the system it runs on cannot be evaluated by an independent party. The TOMS RCR creators concur with the importance of communication, expect collaboration between author and RCR reviewers, share the considerations around reviewer selection, and also put trust in reviewer judgement over numerical bit-wise perfection. A key difference is that for TOMS RCR, authors opt-in with an *RCR Review Request* and the RCR reports are published in the TOMS journal next to the actual papers.

Several journals provide special article types for reproductions of published papers. *Information Sys-*

tems has an invitation only Reproducibility Section for articles describing the reproducibility efforts of published articles, which are co-authored by the original authors and the reproducibility reviewer(s) (see <https://www.elsevier.com/journals/information-systems/0306-4379/guide-for-authors>).

Nature Machine Intelligence recently introduced a new type of article, the reusability report [82]. Inspired by the detailed and nuanced submissions to a reproducibility challenge, the reusability report focuses on the exploration of robustness and generalizability of the original paper's claims [82]. This answers the specific community's challenges around computational reproducibility and also values these kinds of contributions as independent publications, which goes beyond the goals of CODECHECK. The journal *Cortex* has a special article type *Verification Reports*, which are actually about replication of results and are very well designed/reasoned [83]. In a similar vein, the CODECHECK certificates could also be published as a special article type within journals.

Going beyond individual articles, the journal *ReScience C* (<https://rescience.github.io/>) publishes only replications, also requiring open code and replication by a third party. ReScience also relies on free infrastructure (GitHub and Zenodo).

For research with high stakes, where reproduction would be too weak and post-publication replication possibly too late because of policy impact, Benjamin-Chung et al. [84] propose *internal replication*. A workflow that has undergone internal replication would likely be of high quality and relatively easy to check. Similarly, internal CODECHECKs may be used, with the same limitations such as group think [84], to ensure reproducibility before submission. Such internal checks are professionalised in local reproduction services, such as CISER R-squared (<https://ciser.cornell.edu/research/results-reproduction-r-squared-service/>) or YARD (<https://isps.yale.edu/research/data/approach>), or in communities such as Oxford's code review network (<https://github.com/OxfordCodeReviewNet/forum>).

Gavis and Donoho [85] propose a new discipline and infrastructure for reproducible computational research. Their specific packaging format, provenance record, and cryptographic *Verifiable Result Identifier* would indeed provide excellent reproducibility. However, the system is also complex and since its creation in 2011 we are not aware of any publisher using it; also, the system is not open source. In comparison, CODECHECK is less powerful but also much more flexible and less dependent on specific tools or infrastructure. If data and code are deposited properly, i.e., very unlikely to disappear, then the certificate's DOI is practically close to the cryptographic identifier.

Another platform for publishing results of reproductions is *SciGen.Report* (<https://scigen.report/>). It is a community-run independent platform to foster communication on reproducibility. People can report on fully, partially, or failed reproductions of articles after publication.

CODECHECK is uniquely designed to be adopted across journals or events and to build a community of codecheckers. CODECHECK shares its interdisciplinary nature with other community initiatives concerned with reproducibility awareness, education, and support, such as ReproHack (<https://reprohack.github.io/reprohack-hq/>), Code Copilot (https://twitter.com/Code_Copilot),

or Papers with Code (<https://paperswithcode.com/about>). The latter recently announced a collaboration with the preprint server *arXiv* on providing data and code supplements for machine learning manuscripts and runs a reproducibility challenge. Likewise, different disciplines and journals provide reproducibility checklists, e.g., science and engineering [86] or GIScience [87], which naturally share some aspects while addressing particularities as well as addressing researchers from different fields. Regarding the education and guidance for authors, we see CODECHECK's role as referencing and linking educational efforts and helpful material, not as creating and maintaining such content.

Limitations

Isn't CODECHECK what peer review should be doing already? On the surface, yes, but peer reviewers are overburdened enough and asking them to do more work around peer review is not likely to succeed. When an editor (Tsuyoshi Miyakawa) requested raw data from $n=41$ authors before reviewing, 21 authors withdrew their manuscripts; 19 of the 20 remaining articles were rejected after peer review [88]. Such basic checks require effort from editors, yet they only rely on the availability of data files and the content of the paper. These availability checks can be enhanced by having more complex CODECHECKs request the code and then execute it. This might fall within idealistic expectations of peer review, but is rare. Establishing a CODECHECK process acknowledges that peer reviewing practices have been unable to adapt to the challenges of computational papers. The concept of a CODECHECK, just as the concepts of reproducible research and Open Science, may be transitional by nature. If the activities described here as being part of a CODECHECK are integrated into the publication process the initiative will have succeeded.

Should CODECHECK requirements be more demanding? CODECHECK by design does not require authors to provide (and sustain) an eternally functional workflow nor suggests a specific software stack or practical approach. Creating something that anyone can reproduce has been called a fool's errand (<https://twitter.com/DougBlank/status/1135904909663068165>) and we tend to agree. However, the package of data, code, and documentation collaboratively created by authors and codecheckers is a snapshot of a working analysis that greatly increases the likelihood of a successful reproduction and the possibility that a workflow can be extended by third parties in the future, if they have access to suitable resources and matching skill set. Concrete implementations of CODECHECK workflows, especially for specific disciplines, may reify much more helpful guidelines for authors on how to create reproducibility packages. Our author-friendly "low bar" should not stay low forever, but cultural change takes time and the encouragement and guidance that CODECHECK, as part of the widely accepted peer review concept, can provide may eventually allow the bar to be raised much higher, e.g., with executable research compendia [89], "Whole Tales" [90], or continuous analysis [91]. However, considering that missing artefacts and lack of documentation have repeatedly been identified as key barriers to reproducibility (e.g., [92, 29]), we would not underestimate the power of a simple check. For example, ModelDB curation policies require that only one figure need be

manually reproduced [93], but that has not limited the usefulness nor success of the platform. A codechecker does not fulfil the same role as a *statistical reviewer*, as it is applied by some journals in the biomedical domain (cf. [94, 95]). The statistical reviewer evaluates the appropriateness of statistical methods [95] and can support topical reviewers if, e.g., complex methods or sophisticated variants of statistical tests are applied [94]. The codechecker may go equally deep into the review, but only if they have the expertise and time. We can imagine a tiered workflow where a codechecker could, just as a conventional reviewer could, recommend a detailed code review (see next paragraph) to the editor if they come upon certain issues while examining the work.

A codechecker does not conduct a *code review*. Code reviews are valuable to improve reproducibility and reusability, and their proponents even believe they can improve the research [96]. Code reviews, however, have quite different structural challenges and require even more resources. That said, a well-reviewed codebase is likely to be easier to codecheck, and the awareness of high-quality code raised through CODECHECK may lead to more support for code reviewing. Initiatives and journals that conduct software reviews independent of a specific publication or workflow include ROpenSci (<https://ropensci.org/>), PyOpenSci (<https://www.pyopensci.org/>), and JOSS (<https://joss.theoj.org/>). Furthermore, the codechecker's task list is intentionally not overloaded with related issues such as ensuring proper citation of data and software or depositing material in suitable repositories. Nevertheless, codecheckers are free to highlight these issues.

How are failures during checks handled?

We do not yet have a process for denoting if a reproduction fails, as our case-studies were all successful. In the case that a journal adopts CODECHECK for all submissions, the question remains as what to do if a check fails, after exhausting efforts between author and codechecker to reproduce the workflow. A negative comment in a CODECHECK certificate or a failed check does not necessarily mean the paper or research is bad (cf. discussion on negative comments in [17]). We doubt that publicly reporting failures (i.e., the code would not run) will increase overall reproducibility, and may prohibit authors from sharing their work, which is always more desirable than nothing shared. Therefore, we recommend sharing interim reproduction efforts only with the authors, even if that means that volunteer efforts may go unnoticed if no certificate is published. Rosenthal et al. [97] discuss such incentives for different actors around the implementation of reproducibility. We see CODECHECK as one way for organisations to invest in reproducibility by creating incentives until reproducible computations become the norm.

Who will pay for the compute time? For papers that take significant compute time (days, not minutes), it is unclear who will pay for it. One must carefully consider the sustainability of rerunning computations and the environmental impact large calculations, such as training machine learning models, have. A pragmatic workaround is to request that authors provide a “toy” example, or small dataset that can be quickly analysed to demonstrate that the workflow runs correctly.

What about my proprietary software and sensitive data? Given the prevalence of proprietary

software, e.g. MATLAB, we pragmatically decided that we should accept code as long as we could find a machine with suitable licences to run it. However, this prohibits us from using open infrastructure for reproducibility (cf. [10, 98]) and requires the codechecker to have access to that particular software. Non-open software also considerably hampers reuse, especially by researchers from the global south. Therefore, allowing proprietary software is a compromise that should be reconsidered.

Solutions for proprietary and sensitive data exist. Authors can provide synthetic data (cf. [99]), some data can effectively be redacted [100], and publishers or independent entities can provide infrastructure for sharing data and workflows confidentially [101] or with access to derived results but not raw data [99], i.e., data enclaves [102], or domains of reproducibility [103]).

Can't someone cheat? Yes. We simply check that the code runs, not that it is correct or sound science. This “mechanical” test is indeed a low bar. By having code and data openly deposited, third parties can later examine the code, and we hope that knowing the code will be open ensures that authors will not cheat. It also allows researchers, potentially with new methods, to look for errors. This is more effective than engaging in an arms race on building methods to detect malicious intent now with closed datasets and code. This is analogous to storing blood samples of sport champions today to possibly detect doping in the future with more sensitive methods (cf. [104]). Another comparison that helped us define the scope of a CODECHECK is that we think of the codechecker as forensic photographer, capturing details so that an investigator may later scrutinise them.

Who's got time for more peer review? Agree; codechecking takes time that could otherwise be used for traditional peer review. However, a CODECHECK is different from peer review. First, the **technical nature** of a CODECHECK sets clear expectations and thereby time budget compared to conventional peer review. For example, authors are told what to provide and the codechecker can be told when to stop. Codecheckers can always directly ask the author when clarification is required, thereby increasing **efficiency**. Second, the specific skill set of a codechecker allows for **different groups** to participate in the review process. ECRs might be attracted to learn more about recent methods, peer review, and reproducibility practices. Research Software Engineers who might not regularly be involved in writing or reviewing papers might be interested in increasing their connection with scholarly practices. An extra codechecker may simplify the matchmaking an editor does when identifying suitable reviewers for a submission, as technical and topical expertise can be provided by different people. Third, recall that CODECHECKS should always be publicly available, unlike peer review reports. With code and workflows, the codechecker's feedback may directly impact and improve the author's work. The public certificates and contributions provide **peer recognition** for the codechecker. Fourth, we found that focusing on workflow mechanics and interacting with the author makes reproductions **educational**. It also is a different role and, as such, could be a welcome option for researchers to give back their time to the community.

While such benefits are also part of idealistic peer review, they are mostly hidden behind paraphrased anonymous acknowledgement.

Do workflows need to be codechecked multiple times? If a paper is checked at the start of peer review, it might need re-checking if the paper is modified during peer review. This is inevitable, and happened to us [51]. This is desirable though, if interactions between author, reviewer, and codechecker led to improvements. Checking the manuscript the second time is likely to be much less work than the first time.

What does it mean for a figure to be reproducible? Automatically detecting if a codechecker's results are "the same" as an author's is more challenging than it might appear. That is why we do not require results to be *identical* for a CODECHECK to pass but simply that the code runs and generates output files that the author claims. Stochastic simulations mean that often we will get different results, and even the same versions of libraries can generate outputs that differ by operating system [105]. While reproducibility practices can mitigate some of these problems, e.g., by using a seed, the flexibility of the human judgement is still needed, rather than bitwise reproducibility. The codechecker is free to comment on visible differences in outputs in their report.

Shouldn't the next step be more revolutionary? CODECHECK's approach is to acknowledge shortcomings around computational reproducibility and to iteratively improve the current system. It remains to be proven whether this approach is welcomed broadly and if involving publishing stakeholders helps to further the cause. We have discussed more stringent rules at length, e.g. only considering fully free and open source software, diamond Open Access journals, but we eventually decided against them on the level of the principles. For the CODECHECK community process, documented at <https://codecheck.org.uk/guide/community-process>, and the volunteer codechecker community, these requirements can be reconsidered.

We have deliberated requiring modern technologies to support reproducibility (cf. [10]), focusing instead on the human interface and the judgement of experienced researchers and developers as a more sustainable and flexible approach. All types of research can adopt CODECHECK due to its flexible design. CODECHECK could include automated scoring (e.g., [106]), yet automation and metrics bear new risks. The focus of the CODECHECK principles on code execution allows journals and publishers to innovate on financial models and peer review practices at their own pace.

Conclusions and future work

CODECHECK works — we have created a considerable number of certificates to demonstrate it. The creation of certificates and interactions with authors and editors shaped the principles and the workflow and also confirmed the approach taken. This result corroborates findings from similar evaluations of reproducible computational research in journals and conferences. CODECHECKS increase transparency of the checked papers and can contribute to building trust in research findings. The set of shared principles and common name, through recognition value, will allow researchers to judge the level of scrutiny that results have faced. CODECHECK requires direct acknowledgement of the codechecker's contributions, not indirectly via citations of reproductions or informal credit.

CODECHECK however harbours the same limitations as peer review in general and is closely connected to larger disruptions and challenges in scholarly communication [107, 108, 7], including the tensions between commercial publishing and reviewers' often free labour, and a global pandemic that has jumbled up academic publishing and exposed a broader general audience to preprints [109]. Establishing CODECHECK workflows must be seen as interconnected with much larger issues in research, such as broken metrics or malpractice triggered by publication pressure [110, 111]. We certainly do not want the binary attribute of “code works” to become a factor in bibliometric approaches for performance assessments.

While developed for the current “paper”-centric publication process, the CODECHECK principles would also work well with novel publication paradigms, e.g., peer-reviewed computational notebooks [112], iterative and granular communication of research outputs, articles with live-code [113] such as eLife's ERA (see <https://elifesciences.org/labs/dc5acbde/welcome-to-a-new-era-of-reproducible-decentralized-infrastructure-and-public-reviewer-reputation-systems> [114], and completely new visions for scholarly communication and peer review such as described by Amy J. Ko in *A modern vision for peer review* (<https://medium.com/bits-and-behavior/a-modern-vision-for-peer-review-d5f73f0fae0>

An explicit segmentation of research steps could even make the focus of a CODECHECK easier by only checking the “analysis” sub-publication. The discovery of CODECHECKS could be increased by depositing certificates into public databases of reproductions, such as *SciGen.Report*. Public researcher profiles, such as ORCID, may consider different types of reviewer activity to capture how independent code execution contributes to science. Notably, the discussed limitations are largely self-imposed for easier acceptance and evolutionary integration, as to not break the current system and increase demands gradually without leaving practitioners behind.

A CODECHECK system, even if temporarily adopted as a sustainable transition towards more open publication and review practices, can contribute to increased trust in research outputs. Introducing CODECHECK should be informed by lessons learned from (introducing) open peer review [15]. Our conversations with publishers and editors indicate a willingness to adopt open practices like these, but that it is hard to innovate with legacy infrastructure and established practices.

More reproducible practices initiated by CODECHECKS could lead communities to reach a state where authors provide sufficient material and reviewers have acquired sufficient skills that peer reviewers will generally conduct a CODECHECK-level of checking; only in especially sophisticated cases will a specialised codechecker be needed. The main challenge for us remains getting journals to embrace the idea behind CODECHECK and to realise processes that conform to the principles, whether or not they use CODECHECK by name. We would be keen to use the flexibility of the principles and cooperate with journals to learn more about the advantages and yet unclear specific challenges – e.g. do CODECHECKS really work better with open peer review? To facilitate the adoption, the CODECHECK badge is, intentionally, not branded beyond the checkmark and green colour and simply states “code works”.

Future CODECHECK versions may be accompanied by studies to ensure codechecking does not fall into the same traps as peer review did [16] and to ensure positive change within the review system. This *cultural change*, however, is needed for the valuation of the efforts that go into proper evaluation of papers. Journals can help us to answer open questions in our system: What are crucial decisions or pain points? Can authors retract code/data once a CODECHECK has started? What variants of CODECHECKs will be most common? How will open CODECHECKs influence or codevelop with the scope and anonymity of conventional review over time?

The question of training codecheckers is also relevant. We expect a mentoring scheme within the CODECHECK community (experienced codecheckers will provide on-the-job training or serve as fallback advisors). Codecheckers may also be found by collaborating with reproducible research initiatives such as ReproHack (<https://reprohack.github.io/reprohack-hq/>), ReproducibiliTea (<https://reproducibilitea.org/>, [115]), and Repro4Everyone (<https://repro4everyone.org/>, [116]). The initial reaction of researchers to these ideas shows that scholarly peer review should continue on the path towards facilitating sharing and execution of computational workflows.

Competing interests

SJE is on the editorial board at the journal *Scientific Data* until March 2021. DN is reproducibility chair at the Association of Geographic Information Laboratories in Europe's (AGILE) annual conference.

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Author contributions

DN and SJE contributed equally to all aspects of this project.

0.1 Data availability

Repository: Daniel Nüst, Stephen Eglén, & Iain Davies. (2021). codecheckers/register: CODECHECK Register Deposit January 2021 (Version 2021-01) [Data set]. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4486559>
This project contains the following underlying data:

- `register.csv`. List of all CODECHECK certificates with references to repositories and reports.

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike license (CC-BY-SA 4.0 International).

References

- [1] Ben Marwick. How computers broke science – and what we can do to fix it, 2015. URL <http://theconversation.com/how-computers-broke-science-and-what-we-can-do-to-fix-it-49938>.
- [2] Jonathan B. Buckheit and David L. Donoho. WaveLab and Reproducible Research. In Anestis Antoniadis and Georges Oppenheim, editors, *Wavelets and Statistics*, number 103 in Lecture Notes in Statistics, pages 55–81. Springer New York, 1995. ISBN 978-0-387-94564-4 978-1-4612-2544-7. doi:10.1007/978-1-4612-2544-7_5.
- [3] J. Claerbout and M. Karrenbach. Electronic documents give reproducible research a new meaning. In *SEG Technical Program Expanded Abstracts 1992*, SEG Technical Program Expanded Abstracts, pages 601–604. Society of Exploration Geophysicists, 1992. doi:10.1190/1.1822162.
- [4] Timothy H Vines, Arianne Y K Albert, Rose L Andrew, Florence Débarre, Dan G Bock, Michelle T Franklin, Kimberly J Gilbert, Jean-Sébastien Moore, Sébastien Renaut, and Diana J Rennison. The availability of research data declines rapidly with article age. *Curr. Biol.*, 24(1):94–97, January 2014. ISSN 0960-9822, 1879-0445. doi:10.1016/j.cub.2013.11.014.
- [5] Nick Barnes. Publish your computer code: it is good enough. *Nature*, 467(7317):753, October 2010. ISSN 0028-0836, 1476-4687. doi:10.1038/467753a.
- [6] Florian Markowetz. Five selfish reasons to work reproducibly. *Genome Biology*, 16:274, 2015. ISSN 1474-760X. doi:10.1186/s13059-015-0850-7.
- [7] Aileen Fyfe. Mission or money? *Septentrio Conference Series*, September 2019. ISSN 2387-3086. doi:10.7557/5.4963. Keynote at 14th Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing 2019.
- [8] Lorena A. Barba. Terminologies for Reproducible Research. *arXiv:1802.03311 [cs]*, 2018. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1802.03311>.

- [9] Project Jupyter, Matthias Bussonnier, Jessica Forde, Jeremy Freeman, Brian Granger, Tim Head, Chris Holdgraf, Kyle Kelley, Gladys Nalvarte, Andrew Osheroff, M. Pacer, Yuvi Panda, Fernando Perez, Benjamin Ragan-Kelley, and Carol Willing. Binder 2.0 - Reproducible, interactive, sharable environments for science at scale. *Proceedings of the 17th Python in Science Conference*, pages 113–120, 2018. doi:10.25080/Majora-4af1f417-011.
- [10] Markus Konkol, Daniel Nüst, and Laura Goulier. Publishing computational research - a review of infrastructures for reproducible and transparent scholarly communication. *Research Integrity and Peer Review*, 5(1):10, July 2020. ISSN 2058-8615. doi:10.1186/s41073-020-00095-y.
- [11] Victoria Stodden, David H. Bailey, Jonathan Borwein, Randall J. LeVeque, Bill Rider, and William Stein. Setting the Default to Reproducible: Reproducibility in Computational and Experimental Mathematics. Technical report, The Institute for Computational and Experimental Research in Mathematics, February 2013. URL https://icerm.brown.edu/topical_workshops/tw12-5-rcem/icerm_report.pdf.
- [12] Thu-Mai Christian, Amanda Gooch, Todd Vision, and Elizabeth Hull. Journal data policies: Exploring how the understanding of editors and authors corresponds to the policies themselves. *PLOS ONE*, 15(3):e0230281, March 2020. ISSN 1932-6203. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0230281.
- [13] Brian A. Nosek, Jeffrey R. Spies, and Matt Motyl. Scientific Utopia II. Restructuring Incentives and Practices to Promote Truth Over Publishability. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 7(6):615–631, November 2012. ISSN 1745-6916, 1745-6924. doi:10.1177/1745691612459058.
- [14] Daniel Nüst. CODECHECK certificate 2020-025. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.4279275.
- [15] Tony Ross-Hellauer and Edit Görögh. Guidelines for open peer review implementation. *Research Integrity and Peer Review*, 4(1):4, February 2019. ISSN 2058-8615. doi:10.1186/s41073-019-0063-9.
- [16] Jonathan P. Tennant and Tony Ross-Hellauer. The limitations to our understanding of peer review. *Research Integrity and Peer Review*, 5(1):6, April 2020. ISSN 2058-8615. doi:10.1186/s41073-020-00092-1.
- [17] Daniel Quintana and James Heathers. Everything Hertz 123: Authenticated anonymity (with Michael Eisen). *Open Science Framework*, Jan 2020. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/9CFTX.
- [18] Brendan Bouffler. Keynote at deRSE 2019: Delivering on the promise of Research Computing. *TIB AV-PORTAL*, 2019. doi:10.5446/42484. Video recording published in TIB AV-PORTAL.
- [19] Etienne B. Roesch and Nicolas Rougier. New journal for reproduction and replication results. *Nature*, 581(7806):30–30, May 2020. doi:10.1038/d41586-020-01328-2.
- [20] Chris Chambers. Registered Reports, June 2019. URL <https://osf.io/mvdyq/>. Publisher: OSF.
- [21] Iain Davies. CODECHECK certificate 2020-013. *Zenodo*, July 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3947959.

- [22] Philip B. Stark. Before reproducibility must come preproducibility, May 2018.
- [23] Lorena A Barba. Praxis of Reproducible Computational Science. October 2018. doi:10.22541/au.153922477.77361922.
- [24] Nicholas G Davies, Adam J Kucharski, Rosalind M Eggo, Amy Gimma, W John Edmunds, Thibaut Jombart, Kathleen O'Reilly, Akira Endo, Joel Hellewell, Emily S Nightingale, Billy J Quilty, Christopher I Jarvis, Timothy W Russell, Petra Klepac, Nikos I Bosse, Sebastian Funk, Sam Abbott, Graham F Medley, Hamish Gibbs, Carl A B Pearson, Stefan Flasche, Mark Jit, Samuel Clifford, Kiesha Prem, Charlie Diamond, Jon Emery, Arminder K Deol, Simon R Procter, Kevin van Zandvoort, Yueqian Fiona Sun, James D Munday, Alicia Rosello, Megan Auzenbergs, Gwen Knight, Rein M G J Houben, and Yang Liu. Effects of non-pharmaceutical interventions on COVID-19 cases, deaths, and demand for hospital services in the UK: a modelling study. *The Lancet Public Health*, June 2020. ISSN 2468-2667. doi:10.1016/S2468-2667(20)30133-X.
- [25] Adam J. Kucharski, Petra Klepac, Andrew J. K. Conlan, Stephen M. Kissler, Maria L. Tang, Hannah Fry, Julia R. Gog, W. John Edmunds, Jon C. Emery, Graham Medley, James D. Munday, Timothy W. Russell, Quentin J. Leclerc, Charlie Diamond, Simon R. Procter, Amy Gimma, Fiona Yueqian Sun, Hamish P. Gibbs, Alicia Rosello, Kevin van Zandvoort, Stéphane Hué, Sophie R. Meakin, Arminder K. Deol, Gwen Knight, Thibaut Jombart, Anna M. Foss, Nikos I. Bosse, Katherine E. Atkins, Billy J. Quilty, Rachel Lowe, Kiesha Prem, Stefan Flasche, Carl A. B. Pearson, Rein M. G. J. Houben, Emily S. Nightingale, Akira Endo, Damien C. Tully, Yang Liu, Julian Villabona-Arenas, Kathleen O'Reilly, Sebastian Funk, Rosalind M. Eggo, Mark Jit, Eleanor M. Rees, Joel Hellewell, Samuel Clifford, Christopher I. Jarvis, Sam Abbott, Megan Auzenbergs, Nicholas G. Davies, and David Simons. Effectiveness of isolation, testing, contact tracing, and physical distancing on reducing transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in different settings: a mathematical modelling study. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 20(10):1151–1160, October 2020. ISSN 1473-3099, 1474-4457. doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30457-6.
- [26] Dalmeet Singh Chawla. Critiqued coronavirus simulation gets thumbs up from code-checking efforts. *Nature*, June 2020. ISSN 0028-0836. doi:10.1038/d41586-020-01685-y.
- [27] Stephen J. Eglén. CODECHECK certificate 2020-010. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [28] Daniel Nüst, Frank Ostermann, Rusne Sileryte, Barbara Hofer, Carlos Granell, Marta Teperek, Anita Graser, Karl Broman, Kristina Hettne, and Markus Konkol. Reproducible Publications at AGILE Conferences, 2019. URL <https://reproducible-agile.github.io/>.
- [29] Daniel Nüst, Frank Ostermann, Carlos Granell, and Alexander Knoch. Improving reproducibility of geospatial conference papers – lessons learned from a first implementation of reproducibility reviews. *Septentrio Conference Series*, September 2020. ISSN 2387-3086. doi:10.7557/5.5601.
- [30] Stephen J. Eglén. CODECHECK certificate 2020-001. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.

- [31] Stephen R Piccolo, Terry J Lee, Erica Suh, and Kimball Hill. ShinyLearner: A containerized benchmarking tool for machine-learning classification of tabular data. *Gigascience*, 9(4), April 2020. ISSN 2047-217X. doi:10.1093/gigascience/giaa026.
- [32] Stephen J. Eglen and Daniel Nüst. CODECHECK certificate 2020-002. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [33] Peter J B Hancock, Roland J Baddeley, and Leslie S Smith. The principal components of natural images. *Network: Computation in Neural Systems*, 3(1):61–70, 1992. doi:10.1088/0954-898X_3_1_008.
- [34] Daniel Nüst. CODECHECK certificate 2020-003. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [35] J J Hopfield. Neural networks and physical systems with emergent collective computational abilities. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, 79(8):2554–2558, April 1982. ISSN 0027-8424. doi:10.1073/pnas.79.8.2554.
- [36] Daniel Nüst. CODECHECK certificate 2020-004. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [37] A G Barto, R S Sutton, and C W Anderson. Neuronlike adaptive elements that can solve difficult learning control problems. *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern.*, SMC-13(5):834–846, September 1983. ISSN 0018-9472, 2168-2909. doi:10.1109/TSMC.1983.6313077.
- [38] Stephen J. Eglen. CODECHECK certificate 2020-005. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [39] Rene Larisch. [Re] Connectivity reflects coding a model of voltage-based STDP with homeostasis. *ReScience C*, 5(3), November 2019. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.3538217.
- [40] Stephen J. Eglen. CODECHECK certificate 2020-006. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [41] Georgios Detorakis. [Re] A Generalized Linear Integrate-And-Fire Neural Model Produces Diverse Spiking Behaviors. *ReScience C*, 3(1):#7, October 2017. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.1003214.
- [42] Stephen J. Eglen. CODECHECK certificate 2020-007. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:"TODO".
- [43] Pamela Hathway and Dan F. M. Goodman. [Re] Spike Timing Dependent Plasticity Finds The Start Of Repeating Patterns In Continuous Spike Trains. *ReScience C*, 4(1):#6, August 2018. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.1327348.
- [44] Stephen J. Eglen. CODECHECK certificate 2020-008. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [45] Nicholas G Davies, Adam J Kucharski, Rosalind M Eggo, Amy Gimma, CMMID COVID-19 working group, and W John Edmunds. Effects of non-pharmaceutical interventions on COVID-19 cases, deaths, and demand for hospital services in the UK: a modelling study, April 2020. URL https://github.com/cmmid/cmmid.github.io/blob/master/topics/covid19/reports/uk_scenario_modelling_preprint_2020_04_01.pdf.

- [46] Stephen J. Eglén. CODECHECK certificate 2020-009. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [47] Adam J Kucharski, Petra Klepac, Andrew J. K. Conlan, Stephen M. Kissler, Maria Tang, Hannah Fry, Julia R. Gog, W. John Edmunds, and CMMID COVID-19 working group. Effectiveness of isolation, testing, contact tracing and physical distancing on reducing transmission of sars-cov-2 in different settings: a mathematical modelling study, April 2020. URL https://cmmid.github.io/topics/covid19/reports/bbc_contact_tracing.pdf.
- [48] N. Ferguson, D. Laydon, G. Nedjati Gilani, N. Imai, K. Ainslie, M. Baguelin, S. Bhatia, A. Boonyasiri, Z. Cucunuba Perez, G. Cuomo-Dannenburg, A. Dighe, I. Dorigatti, H. Fu, K. Gaythorpe, W. Green, A. Hamlet, W. Hinsley, L. Okell, S. Van Elsland, H. Thompson, R. Verity, E. Volz, H. Wang, Y. Wang, P. Walker, C. Walters, P. Winskill, C. Whittaker, C. Donnelly, S. Riley, and A. Ghani. Report 9: Impact of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) to reduce COVID19 mortality and healthcare demand. March 2020. doi:10.25561/77482.
- [49] Stephen J. Eglén. CODECHECK certificate 2020-011. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [50] Seth Flaxman, Swapnil Mishra, Axel Gandy, H. Juliette T. Unwin, Thomas A. Mellan, Helen Coupland, Charles Whittaker, Harrison Zhu, Tresnia Berah, Jeffrey W. Eaton, Mélodie Monod, Azra C. Ghani, Christl A. Donnelly, Steven Riley, Michaela A. C. Vollmer, Neil M. Ferguson, Lucy C. Okell, and Samir Bhatt. Estimating the effects of non-pharmaceutical interventions on COVID-19 in Europe. *Nature*, 584(7820):257–261, August 2020. ISSN 1476-4687. doi:10.1038/s41586-020-2405-7.
- [51] Stephen J. Eglén. CODECHECK certificate 2020-012. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3893617.
- [52] H. Unwin, S. Mishra, V. C. Bradley, A. Gandy, M. Vollmer, T. Mellan, H. Coupland, K. Ainslie, C. Whittaker, J. Ish-Horowicz, S. Filippi, X. Xi, M. Monod, O. Ratmann, M. Hutchinson, F. Valka, H. Zhu, I. Hawryluk, P. Milton, M. Baguelin, A. Boonyasiri, N. Brazeau, L. Cattarino, G. Charles, L. Cooper, Z. Cucunuba Perez, G. Cuomo-Dannenburg, A. Djaafara, I. Dorigatti, O. Eales, J. Eaton, S. Van Elsland, R. Fitzjohn, K. Gaythorpe, W. Green, T. Hallett, W. Hinsley, N. Imai, B. Jeffrey, E. Knock, D. Laydon, J. Lees, G. Nedjati Gilani, P. Nouvellet, L. Okell, A. Ower, K. Parag, I. Siveroni, H. Thompson, R. Verity, P. Walker, C. Walters, Y. Wang, O. Watson, L. Whittles, A. Ghani, N. Ferguson, S. Riley, C. Donnelly, S. Bhatt, and S. Flaxman. Report 23: State-level tracking of COVID-19 in the United States. May 2020. doi:10.25561/79231.
- [53] H. Juliette T. Unwin, Swapnil Mishra, Valerie C. Bradley, Axel Gandy, Thomas A. Mellan, Helen Coupland, Jonathan Ish-Horowicz, Michaela A. C. Vollmer, Charles Whittaker, Sarah L. Filippi, Xiaoyue Xi, Mélodie Monod, Oliver Ratmann, Michael Hutchinson, Fabian Valka, Harrison Zhu, Iwona Hawryluk, Philip Milton, Kylie E. C. Ainslie, Marc Baguelin, Adhiratha Boonyasiri, Nick F. Brazeau, Lorenzo Cattarino, Zulma Cucunuba, Gina Cuomo-Dannenburg, Ilaria Dorigatti, Oliver D. Eales, Jeffrey W. Eaton, Sabine L. van Elsland, Richard G. FitzJohn, Katy A. M. Gaythorpe, William Green, Wes Hinsley, Benjamin Jeffrey, Edward Knock, Daniel J. Laydon, John Lees, Gemma Nedjati-Gilani, Pierre Nouvellet, Lucy Okell, Kris V. Parag, Igor Siveroni, Hayley A. Thompson, Patrick

- Walker, Caroline E. Walters, Oliver J. Watson, Lilith K. Whittles, Azra C. Ghani, Neil M. Ferguson, Steven Riley, Christl A. Donnelly, Samir Bhatt, and Seth Flaxman. State-level tracking of COVID-19 in the United States. *Nature Communications*, 11(1):6189, December 2020. ISSN 2041-1723. doi:10.1038/s41467-020-19652-6.
- [54] Manuel Spitschan, Corrado Garbazza, Susanne Kohl, and Christian Cajochen. Rest-activity cycles and melatonin phase angle of circadian entrainment in people without cone-mediated vision. *bioRxiv*, 2020. doi:10.1101/2020.06.02.129502.
- [55] Iain Davies. CODECHECK certificate 2020-014. July 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3967326.
- [56] Sadra Sadeh and Claudia Clopath. Patterned perturbation of inhibition can reveal the dynamical structure of neural processing. *eLife*, 9:e52757, February 2020. ISSN 2050-084X. doi:10.7554/elife.52757.
- [57] Iain Davies. CODECHECK certificate 2020-015. August 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3978402. See file LICENSE for license of the contained code. The report document codecheck.pdf is published under CC-BY 4.0 International.
- [58] Jyun you Liou, Elliot H Smith, Lisa M Bateman, Samuel L Bruce, Guy M McKhann, Robert R Goodman, Ronald G Emerson, Catherine A Schevon, and LF Abbott. A model for focal seizure onset, propagation, evolution, and progression. *eLife*, 9:e50927, March 2020. ISSN 2050-084X. doi:10.7554/elife.50927.
- [59] Daniel Nüst. CODECHECK certificate 2020-016. June 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3981253.
- [60] Chris Brunsdon and Alexis Comber. Opening practice: supporting reproducibility and critical spatial data science. *Journal of Geographical Systems*, August 2020. doi:10.1007/s10109-020-00334-2.
- [61] Daniel Nüst. CODECHECK certificate 2020-017. August 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.4003848.
- [62] Roger S. Bivand. Progress in the r ecosystem for representing and handling spatialdata. *Journal of Geographical Systems*, 2020. doi:10.1007/s10109-020-00336-0.
- [63] Daniel Nüst. Reproducibility review of: Integrating cellular automata and discrete global grid systems: a case study into wildfire modelling. 2020. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/ZTC7M.
- [64] Majid Hojati and Colin Robertson. Integrating cellular automata and discrete global grid systems: a case study into wildfire modelling. *AGILE: GIScience Series*, 1:1–23, July 2020. doi:10.5194/agile-giss-1-6-2020.
- [65] Daniel Nüst and Carlos Granell. Reproducibility review of: What to do in the meantime: A service coverage analysis for parked autonomous vehicles. 2020. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/5SVMT.
- [66] Steffen Illium, Philipp Andreas Friese, Robert Müller, and Sebastian Feld. What to do in the meantime: A service coverage analysis for parked autonomous vehicles. *AGILE: GIScience Series*, 1:1–15, July 2020. doi:10.5194/agile-giss-1-7-2020.

- [67] Daniel Nüst and Frank Ostermann. Reproducibility review of: Window operators for processing spatio-temporal data streams on unmanned vehicles. 2020. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/7TWR2.
- [68] Tobias Werner and Thomas Brinkhoff. Window operators for processing spatio-temporal data streams on unmanned vehicles. *AGILE: GIScience Series*, 1:1–23, July 2020. doi:10.5194/agile-giss-1-21-2020.
- [69] Frank Ostermann and Daniel Nüst. Reproducibility review of: Comparing supervised learning algorithms for spatial nominal entity recognition. 2020. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/SUWPJ.
- [70] Amine Medad, Mauro Gaio, Ludovic Moncla, Sébastien Mustière, and Yannick Le Nir. Comparing supervised learning algorithms for spatial nominal entity recognition. *AGILE: GIScience Series*, 1: 1–18, July 2020. doi:10.5194/agile-giss-1-15-2020.
- [71] Daniel Nüst. Reproducibility review of: Extracting interrogative intents and concepts from geo-analytic questions. 2020. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/7XRQG.
- [72] Haiqi Xu, Ehsan Hamzei, Enkhbold Nyamsuren, Han Kruijer, Stephan Winter, Martin Tomko, and Simon Scheider. Extracting interrogative intents and concepts from geo-analytic questions. *AGILE: GIScience Series*, 1:1–21, July 2020. doi:10.5194/agile-giss-1-23-2020.
- [73] Frank Ostermann and Daniel Nüst. Reproducibility review of: Tracking hurricane dorian in gdel and twitter. 2020. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/XS5YR.
- [74] Innocensia Owuor, Hartwig H. Hochmair, and Sreten Cvetojevic. Tracking hurricane dorian in GDELT and twitter. *AGILE: GIScience Series*, 1:1–18, July 2020. doi:10.5194/agile-giss-1-19-2020.
- [75] Stephen J. Eglén. CODECHECK certificate 2020-024. *Zenodo*, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.4310025.
- [76] Diogo Munaro Vieira, Chrystinne Fernandes, Carlos Lucena, and Sérgio Lifschitz. Driftage: a multi-agent system for concept drift detection and an application on electromyography. *Gigascience*, (under review), 2020. ISSN 2047-217X. URL <https://github.com/dmvieira/driftage>.
- [77] Francesco Carrer, Tomasz M. Kossowski, Justyna Wilk, Michał B. Pietrzak, and Roger S. Bivand. The application of Local Indicators for Categorical Data (LICD) to explore spatial dependence in archaeological spaces. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 126:105306, February 2021. ISSN 0305-4403. doi:10.1016/j.jas.2020.105306.
- [78] Daniel Nüst, Stephen Eglén, and Iain Davies. codecheckers/register: CODECHECK Register Deposit January 2021, September 2020. URL <https://codecheck.org.uk/register/>.
- [79] Stephen Eglén and Daniel Nüst. codecheckers/codecheck: codecheck R package version 0.1.0, February 2021. URL <https://zenodo.org/record/4522507>.
- [80] Emmanuel Blondel. *zen4R: Interface to 'Zenodo' REST API*, 2020. URL <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=zen4R>. R package version 0.4-2.

- [81] Michael A. Heroux. Editorial: ACM TOMS Replicated Computational Results Initiative. *ACM Transactions on Mathematical Software*, 41(3):13:1–13:5, June 2015. ISSN 0098-3500. doi:10.1145/2743015.
- [82] Research, reuse, repeat. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 2(12):729–729, December 2020. ISSN 2522-5839. doi:10.1038/s42256-020-00277-9.
- [83] Christopher D. Chambers. Verification Reports: A new article type at Cortex. *Cortex*, 129:A1–A3, August 2020. ISSN 0010-9452. doi:10.1016/j.cortex.2020.04.020.
- [84] Jade Benjamin-Chung, John M. Colford, Jr., Andrew Mertens, Alan E. Hubbard, and Benjamin F. Arnold. Internal replication of computational workflows in scientific research. *Gates Open Research*, 4:17, June 2020. ISSN 2572-4754. doi:10.12688/gatesopenres.13108.2.
- [85] Matan Gavish and David Donoho. A Universal Identifier for Computational Results. *Procedia Computer Science*, 4:637–647, January 2011. ISSN 1877-0509. doi:10.1016/j.procs.2011.04.067.
- [86] David E. Rosenberg, Yves Filion, Rebecca Teasley, Samuel Sandoval-Solis, Jory S. Hecht, Jakobus E. van Zyl, George F. McMahan, Jeffery S. Horsburgh, Joseph R. Kasprzyk, and David G. Tarboton. The Next Frontier: Making Research More Reproducible. *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 146(6):01820002, June 2020. ISSN 1943-5452. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0001215.
- [87] Daniel Nüst, Frank Ostermann, Rusne Sileryte, Barbara Hofer, Carlos Granell, Marta Teperek, Anita Graser, Karl Broman, and Kristina Hettne. *AGILE Reproducible Paper Guidelines*. OSF, 2019.
- [88] Tsuyoshi Miyakawa. No raw data, no science: another possible source of the reproducibility crisis. *Molecular Brain*, 13(1):24, February 2020. ISSN 1756-6606. doi:10.1186/s13041-020-0552-2.
- [89] Daniel Nst, Markus Konkol, Edzer Pebesma, Christian Kray, Marc Schutzeichel, Holger Przibytzin, and Jörg Lorenz. Opening the Publication Process with Executable Research Compendia. *D-Lib Magazine*, 23(1/2), January 2017. ISSN 1082-9873. doi:10.1045/january2017-nuest.
- [90] Adam Brinckman, Kyle Chard, Niall Gaffney, Mihael Hategan, Matthew B. Jones, Kacper Kowalik, Sivakumar Kulasekaran, Bertram Ludäscher, Bryce D. Mecum, Jarek Nabrzyski, Victoria Stodden, Ian J. Taylor, Matthew J. Turk, and Kandace Turner. Computing environments for reproducibility: Capturing the “Whole Tale”. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 2018. ISSN 0167-739X. doi:10.1016/j.future.2017.12.029.
- [91] Brett K. Beaulieu-Jones and Casey S. Greene. Reproducibility of computational workflows is automated using continuous analysis. *Nature Biotechnology*, 35(4):342–346, April 2017. ISSN 1546-1696. doi:10.1038/nbt.3780.
- [92] James H. Stagge, David E. Rosenberg, Adel M. Abdallah, Hadia Akbar, Nour A. Attallah, and Ryan James. Assessing data availability and research reproducibility in hydrology and water resources. *Scientific Data*, 6(1):190030, February 2019. ISSN 2052-4463. doi:10.1038/sdata.2019.30.

- [93] Robert A. McDougal, Anna S. Bulanova, and William W. Lytton. Reproducibility in Computational Neuroscience Models and Simulations. *IEEE transactions on bio-medical engineering*, 63(10):2021–2035, October 2016. ISSN 0018-9294. doi:10.1109/TBME.2016.2539602.
- [94] Mladen Petrovečki. The role of statistical reviewer in biomedical scientific journal. *Biochemia Medica*, 19(3):223–230, October 2009. doi:10.11613/BM.2009.020.
- [95] Darren C. Greenwood and Jennifer V. Freeman. How to spot a statistical problem: advice for a non-statistical reviewer. *BMC Medicine*, 13(1):270, November 2015. ISSN 1741-7015. doi:10.1186/s12916-015-0510-5.
- [96] Marian Petre and Greg Wilson. Code Review For and By Scientists. *arXiv:1407.5648 [cs]*, September 2014. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1407.5648>. arXiv: 1407.5648.
- [97] Paul Rosenthal, Rudolf Mayer, Kevin Page, Rainer Stotzka, and Evelyne Viegas. Incentives and barriers to reproducibility: Investments and returns. In Juliana Freire, Norbert Fuhr, and Andreas Rauber, editors, *Reproducibility of data-oriented experiments in e-Science*, volume 6 of *Dagstuhl reports*, pages 148–151. Schloss Dagstuhl–Leibniz-Zentrum fuer Informatik, Dagstuhl, Germany, January 2016. doi:10.4230/DagRep.6.1.108. ISSN: 2192-5283.
- [98] Jeffrey M. Perkel. Make code accessible with these cloud services. *Nature*, 575:247–248, November 2019. doi:10.1038/d41586-019-03366-x.
- [99] Jerry Shannon and Kyle Walker. Opening GIScience: A process-based approach. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 32(10):1911–1926, October 2018. ISSN 1365-8816. doi:10.1080/13658816.2018.1464167.
- [100] John O’Loughlin, Pauliina Raento, Joanne P. Sharp, James D. Sidaway, and Philip E. Steinberg. Data ethics: Pluralism, replication, conflicts of interest, and standards in Political Geography. *Political Geography*, 44:A1–A3, January 2015. ISSN 0962-6298. doi:10.1016/j.polgeo.2014.11.001.
- [101] Christophe Pérignon, Kamel Gadouche, Christophe Hurlin, Roxane Silberman, and Eric Debonnel. Certify reproducibility with confidential data. *Science*, 365(6449):127–128, 2019. ISSN 0036-8075, 1095-9203. doi:10.1126/science.aaw2825.
- [102] Ian Foster. Research Infrastructure for the Safe Analysis of Sensitive Data. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 675(1):102–120, January 2018. ISSN 0002-7162. doi:10.1177/0002716217742610.
- [103] Richard Harris, David O’Sullivan, Mark Gahegan, Martin Charlton, Lex Comber, Paul Longley, Chris Brunson, Nick Malleson, Alison Heppenstall, Alex Singleton, Daniel Arribas-Bel, and Andy Evans. More bark than bytes? Reflections on 21+ years of geocomputation. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 44(4):598–617, July 2017. ISSN 2399-8083. doi:10.1177/2399808317710132.

- [104] Daniel Quintana and James Heathers. Everything Hertz 97: Slow science. *Open Science Framework*, Dec 2019. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/XEU42.
- [105] Ed H B M Gronenschild, Petra Habets, Heidi I L Jacobs, Ron Mengelers, Nico Rozendaal, Jim van Os, and Machteld Marcelis. The effects of FreeSurfer version, workstation type, and macintosh operating system version on anatomical volume and cortical thickness measurements. *PLoS One*, 7(6):e38234, June 2012. ISSN 1932-6203. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0038234.
- [106] Joe Menke, Martijn Roelandse, Burak Ozyurt, Maryann Martone, and Anita Bandrowski. The Rigor and Transparency Index Quality Metric for Assessing Biological and Medical Science Methods. *iScience*, 23(11), November 2020. ISSN 2589-0042. doi:10.1016/j.isci.2020.101698.
- [107] Stephen J. Eglén, Ross Mounce, Laurent Gatto, Adrian M. Currie, and Yvonne Nobis. Recent developments in scholarly publishing to improve research practices in the life sciences. *Emerging Topics in Life Sciences*, 2(6):775–778, 2018. ISSN 2397-8554, 2397-8562. doi:10.1042/ETLS20180172.
- [108] Jonathan P. Tennant, Harry Crane, Tom Crick, Jacinto Davila, Asura Enkhbayar, Johanna Havemann, Bianca Kramer, Ryan Martin, Paola Masuzzo, Andy Nobes, Curt Rice, Bárbara Rivera-López, Tony Ross-Hellauer, Susanne Sattler, Paul D. Thacker, and Marc Vanholsbeeck. Ten Hot Topics around Scholarly Publishing. *Publications*, 7(2):34, 2019. doi:10.3390/publications7020034.
- [109] Marcus Munafo. What you need to know about how coronavirus is changing science, May 2020. URL <http://theconversation.com/what-you-need-to-know-about-how-coronavirus-is-changing-science-137641>.
- [110] Heather Piwowar. Altmetrics: Value all research products. *Nature*, 493:159, 2013. ISSN 1476-4687. doi:10.1038/493159a.
- [111] B. A. Nosek, G. Alter, G. C. Banks, D. Borsboom, S. D. Bowman, S. J. Breckler, S. Buck, C. D. Chambers, G. Chin, G. Christensen, M. Contestabile, A. Dafoe, E. Eich, J. Freese, R. Glennerster, D. Goroff, D. P. Green, B. Hesse, M. Humphreys, J. Ishiyama, D. Karlan, A. Kraut, A. Lupia, P. Mabry, T. Madon, N. Malhotra, E. Mayo-Wilson, M. McNutt, E. Miguel, E. Levy Paluck, U. Simonsohn, C. Soderberg, B. A. Spellman, J. Turitto, G. VandenBos, S. Vazire, E. J. Wagenmakers, R. Wilson, and T. Yarkoni. Promoting an open research culture. *Science*, 348(6242):1422–1425, June 2015. ISSN 0036-8075, 1095-9203. doi:10.1126/science.aab2374.
- [112] EarthCube. New EarthCube Peer-Reviewed Jupyter Notebooks Now Available, 2020. URL <https://www.earthcube.org/notebooks>.
- [113] Jeffrey M. Perkel. Pioneering ‘live-code’ article allows scientists to play with each other’s results. *Nature*, 567(7746):17–18, February 2019. doi:10.1038/d41586-019-00724-7.
- [114] Antonio Tenorio-Fornés, Viktor Jacynycz, David Llop-Vila, Antonio Sánchez-Ruiz, and Samer Hassan. Towards a Decentralized Process for Scientific Publication and Peer Review using Blockchain and

IPFS. January 2019. ISBN 978-0-9981331-2-6. doi:10.24251/HICSS.2019.560. Accepted: 2019-01-03T00:29:12Z.

- [115] Lily Fitzgibbon, Daniel Brady, Anthony Haffey, Vanessa Kurdi, Johnny Lau, Jasmine Raw, Etienne Roesch, and Brendan Williams. Brewing up a storm: developing Open Research culture through ReproducibiliTea. *Report*, 2020. doi:10.17864/1926.92781. Central Archive at the University of Reading.
- [116] Susann Auer, Nele Haelterman, Tracey Weissgerber, Jeffrey C. Erlich, Damar Susilaradeya, Magdalena Julkowska, Małgorzata Anna Gazda, Angela Abitua, Anzela Niraulu, Aparna Shah, April Clyburne-Sherin, Benoit Guiquel, Bradly Alicea, Caroline LaManna, Diep Ganguly, Eric J. Perkins, Helena Jambor, Ian Man Ho Li, Jennifer Tsang, Joanne Kamens, Lenny Teytelman, Mariella Paul, Santosh Phuyal, Nicolas Schmelling, Peter Crisp, Sarvenaz Sarabipour, Sonali Roy, Susanna Bachle, MR Tuan Khoi Tran, Tyler Ford, Vicky Steeves, Vinodh Ilangovan, Benjamin Schwessinger, and Nafisa Jadavji. Reproducibility for everyone: a community-led initiative with global reach in reproducible research training. *OSF Preprints*, October 2020. doi:10.31219/osf.io/dxw67.